

Mirdovidov B.*independent researcher of Tashkent State University of Economics***ABSTRACT**

In the context of the global transition to a sustainable economic development model, commercial banks play a key role in mobilizing financial resources for environmentally oriented projects. Green finance is becoming an important tool for mitigating climate risks and stimulating sustainable investment. This article examines modern green finance mechanisms in commercial banks, analyzes international standards and practices for their application, and identifies the main challenges and limitations to the development of this area. Based on the analysis, directions for improving green finance mechanisms in banks are substantiated, aimed at increasing the efficiency of capital allocation, reducing greenwashing risks, and strengthening investor and borrower confidence.

Keywords: Green finance, commercial banks, sustainable development, green loans, green bonds, ESG, climate risks, greenwashing.

1. Introduction.

The modern banking system operates in a context of transformation of the global financial architecture, driven by increasing environmental and climate risks. Climate change, increasing anthropogenic pressure on the environment, and the need to decarbonize the economy are creating new demands on the operations of financial institutions, including commercial banks. In this context, green finance is becoming a priority area of banking activity, focused on supporting projects in renewable energy, energy efficiency, sustainable infrastructure, and environmentally friendly technologies. Commercial banks, with their significant lending potential and developed client base, are key intermediaries in the redistribution of financial resources in favor of sustainable projects.

However, the implementation of green finance in the banking sector faces a number of challenges, including insufficient standardization of green project evaluation criteria, limited environmental risk management tools, and the risk of financial products being unfairly marketed as “green”. This necessitates improving green finance mechanisms in commercial banks, taking into account international experience and sustainable finance standards. The purpose of this article is to analyze existing green financing mechanisms in commercial banks and develop directions for their improvement in the context of sustainable development of the financial system.

2. Theoretical aspects of the research.

The term “green finance” began to emerge in the early 21st century, in an attempt to link business projects and environmentally responsible behavior by economic entities. However, the initial development of this new area of financing was relatively slow, given the traditional skepticism of much of society: human history offers few reasons to expect entrepreneurs to voluntarily constrain themselves by environmental regulations or sacrifice income for the sake of sustainable development goals.

PK Ozili’s approach to green finance is based on its ability to accumulate capital for environmentally significant projects that provide both financial returns and environmental conservation¹. Y.Wang and Q.Zhi define the essence of “green” finance as the integration of environmental protection objectives and the achievement of economic benefits². S.Bahl views green finance as the financing of environmentally friendly activities, green technological solutions and projects, as well as projects to minimize environmental damage³. X.Zhou, X.Tang, R.Zhang define green finance as the process of using financial resources to finance projects and enterprises that have a positive impact on the environment and society as a whole, including in the areas of ecology, energy, sustainable development and climate solutions⁴. D.Klein views green finance not only from the perspective of positive environmental impact, but also as an effective tool for achieving financial profit⁵. The “green” financing mechanism refers to a set of methods for organizing financial and economic relations between entities within the framework of the “green” financing instrument.

¹Ozili P.K. Digital finance, green finance and social finance: Is there a link? / P.K.Ozili // Financial Internet Quarterly. No. 17. P. 1-7. ISSN 2719-3454.

²Wang Y. The role of green finance in environmental protection: Two aspects of market mechanism and policies / Y.Wang, Q.Zhi // Energy Procedia. 2016. No. 104. P. 311-316. ISSN 1876-6102.

³Bahl, S. Green banking The new strategic imperative /S.Bahl //Asian Journal of Research in Business Economics and Management. 2012. No. 2. P. 176-185. ISSN 2249-7307.

⁴Zhou X. Impact of green finance on economic development and environmental quality: a study based on provincial panel data from China / X.Zhou, X.Tang, R.Zhang/Environmental Science and Pollution Research. 2020. No. 27. P.19915-19932. ISSN 0944-1344.

⁵Klein D. The Paris Agreement on Climate Change: Analysis and Commentary/D.Klein. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017. 447 p. ISBN 978-0-19-880376-8.

Categories of green financing instruments⁶

Green finance instruments			
Traditional instruments		Innovative tools	
Green bonds	Green loans	Green crowdfunding, crowdlending, crowdinvesting	Green venture capital investments
Green grants	Green subsidies		
Green loans	Syndicated green loans		
Green Mutual Funds	Investment tax credit		
Budgetary investments	Green certificates		

Green finance in Uzbekistan is in its infancy and faces a number of significant challenges, including an insufficient legal framework, limited financial incentives for private investors, and a lack of knowledge and experience among key players. However, with political will and the active participation of international partners, all the prerequisites are in place to overcome these obstacles. Developing green finance in Uzbekistan will require a comprehensive approach, including improving the legislative framework, creating incentive mechanisms for private investors, and raising awareness and skills among all stakeholders.

Improving mechanisms for balancing incentives and stop factors in the use of market-based green financial instruments. Increasing the importance of the green standards system with increased government oversight of financial institutions and improved reporting transparency requirements. Creating a platform for exchanging credit information on green projects for Chinese manufacturing entities. Emphasis is placed on expanding communications between regions, which will allow for synergies in the approved financial policies in the provinces. International cooperation and capital inflow. Given the rapid development of global green finance, China is actively strengthening cooperation in the field of green financial standards. For example, China and the European Union are already cooperating in the field of green finance. Both sides are striving to create a unified international system of green financial standards⁷.

3. Methodological aspects of the research.

The methodological basis of the study is based on general scientific and specialized methods of analyzing economic processes. The study utilized methods of analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, and a systems approach, which allowed for the examination of green finance mechanisms as an element of a comprehensive banking management system⁸.

A comparative analysis was used to study international practices of green banking finance and compare approaches used in countries with developed financial infrastructure⁹. Economic and statistical methods were used to analyze data on the growth of green loans and bonds in the banking sector. An institutional approach

allowed us to assess the impact of international ESG standards and regulatory requirements on the development of green finance banking mechanisms. The research's information base included reports from international financial institutions, regulatory documents, and scientific publications by international researchers.

4. International experience of the research.

International experience in implementing and developing green finance in commercial banks demonstrates a diversity of approaches, tools, and strategies aimed at integrating ESG criteria and sustainable practices into banking activities.

One of the key global initiatives is the Alliance for Green Commercial Banks, an international platform created with the participation of the International Finance Corporation (IFC, part of the World Bank). The association brings together commercial banks from various countries seeking to integrate sustainable finance into their business models, share best practices, and develop projects in the area of climate solutions and economic adaptation to climate change. This cooperation demonstrates banks' growing commitment to the transition to sustainable growth and is consistent with international green finance standards¹⁰. Green financial products are also actively developing in banking practices in some countries. For example, New Resource Bank (USA) specializes in lending to companies that contribute to sustainable development and environmental initiatives, focusing its loans exclusively on sustainable business models and environmentally sound projects¹¹.

Sustainable banking lending is also gaining significant momentum in Europe. Triodos Bank (Netherlands) follows strict environmental criteria when selecting projects, financing only those initiatives deemed environmentally friendly and socially responsible, excluding companies with a high negative environmental impact¹². Another example is Commerzbank (Germany), which not only finances green projects (including through the issuance of green bonds), but also implements a policy of phasing out financing from the

⁶Anton Vyacheslavovich Piskarev, "Transformation of Green Financing Mechanisms to Ensure National Environmental Well-Being", dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Economic Sciences, Moscow, 2025.

⁷<https://www.climatepolicyinitiative.org/publication/green-banking-in-china-emerging-trends/>

⁸OECD. Developing Sustainable Finance Definitions and Taxonomies, Paris, 2021.

⁹International Capital Market Association (ICMA). Green Bond Principles, London, 2023.

¹⁰Alliance for Green Commercial Banks: Supporting Sustainable Banking and Climate Finance, Washington, DC: World Bank Group, 2025. (<https://www.ifc.org/en/pressroom/2025/ifc-s-alliance-for-green-commercial-banks-welcomes-20-banks-to-support-sustainable>)

¹¹New Resource Bank (URL:https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/New_Resource_Bank)

¹²https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Triodos_Bank

coal industry and uses science-based approaches to decarbonize its investment portfolio¹³. In Asia, commercial banks are also actively developing green products. Sustainable finance programs, such as the Bank of the

Philippines' (BPI) Sustainable Energy Finance (SEF), include support for renewable energy and energy efficiency projects, as well as the development of environmental and social risk management standards¹⁴.

2-table.

International experience of green financing in commercial banks¹⁵

Country / Region	Commercial bank	Main mechanisms of green financing	Results and Features
EU (Netherlands)	Triodos Bank	Green lending, strict ESG screening of projects	Only environmentally and socially sustainable projects are financed.
EU (Germany)	Commerzbank	Green bonds, divestment from coal financing	Reducing the carbon footprint of the loan portfolio
USA	New Resource Bank	Green loans, sustainable corporate finance	Supporting small and medium-sized businesses in the field of sustainable development
China	State-owned commercial banks	National Green Taxonomy, preferential green lending	Growth in green loans and government support for renewable energy projects
Developing countries	Bank members of the Alliance for Green Commercial Banks	ESG integration, climate finance	Expanding access to green financial instruments

Furthermore, the experience of large banking groups, such as the implementation of strategic climate partnerships by players such as BBVA, points to a trend towards closely integrating sustainable finance and climate change strategies into the corporate strategies of global financial institutions¹⁶. Thus, international practice shows that commercial banks are using a full range of green financing instruments from specialized green loan products and green bonds to the implementation of sustainable risk management standards and participation in global alliances supporting sustainable finance. These approaches contribute to the expansion of commercial banks' role in mobilizing private capital for environmental projects and strengthening the global financial transition to sustainable development.

5. Analysis and results of the research.

The analysis showed that commercial banks currently use the following main mechanisms of green financing: green lending, issuance and placement of green bonds, project financing of environmental initiatives and the introduction of ESG criteria into lending policies¹⁷. The most common instrument is green lending, which focuses on financing energy-efficient projects and renewable energy sources. However, the lack of uniform criteria for assessing the environmental sustainability of projects leads to increased operational and reputational risks for banks. In this context, the application of sustainability taxonomies and disclosure standards helps improve the transparency of banking operations.

The research's findings demonstrate that integrating ESG factors into credit analysis and risk management processes enables commercial banks not only to mitigate climate and transition risks but also to enhance long-term financial resilience. However, developing economies face limitations related to insufficient institutional support and a shortage of qualified green finance professionals.

6. Conclusion.

The study found that improving green financing mechanisms in commercial banks is an objectively necessary condition for ensuring the sustainable development of the modern financial system in the face of increasing climate and environmental challenges. Commercial banks, as key financial intermediaries, possess significant potential for mobilizing and redistributing financial resources toward environmentally sustainable and socially significant projects.

The effective use of green financial instruments, including green lending, the issuance and placement of green bonds, and the integration of ESG criteria into credit analysis and risk management processes, contributes to a more rational capital allocation and the mitigation of systemic climate risks. Integrating environmental factors into banking operations allows for the consideration of the long-term consequences of investment decisions and increases the resilience of banking portfolios to the risks of the transition to a low-carbon economy. The research's results also demonstrate that international experience confirms the high effectiveness of a comprehensive approach to developing green

¹³<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Commerzbank>

¹⁴Sustainable finance: Greening the banking sector, Manila, 2024.

URL:<https://www.bworldonline.com/opinion/2024/10/11/627075/sustainable-finance-greening-the-banking-sector/>

¹⁵ Prepared by author.

¹⁶BBVA and KKR form climate-focused strategic partnership, London, 27 September 2024. URL:<https://www.reuters.com/sustainability/sustainable-finance-reporting/bbva-krk-form-climate-focused-strategic-partnership-2024-09-27/>

¹⁷World Bank. Green Finance and Banking Report, Washington, DC, 2023.

finance, combining market mechanisms, voluntary standards, and regulatory instruments.

At the same time, it was revealed that the further development of green finance in commercial banks requires institutional support, improved regulatory frameworks, and the development of a unified methodological approach to assessing the environmental sustainability of projects. Of particular importance is the development of human capital and digital monitoring and reporting tools to improve the transparency and comparability of green finance transactions.

Improving green finance mechanisms in commercial banks not only contributes to achieving environmental and climate goals, but also creates the conditions for long-term financial stability, increased investment attractiveness of the banking sector, and sustainable economic growth overall.

References

1. Alliance for Green Commercial Banks: Supporting Sustainable Banking and Climate Finance, Washington, DC: World Bank Group, 2025. (<https://www.ifc.org/en/pressroom/2025/ifc-s-alliance-for-green-commercial-banks-welcomes-20-banks-to-support-sustainable>)
2. Bahl, S. Green banking – The new strategic imperative / S. Bahl // Asian Journal of Research in Business Economics and Management. – 2012. – No. 2. – P. 176-185. – ISSN 2249–7307.
3. BBVA and KKR form climate-focused strategic partnership, London, 27 September 2024. URL: <https://www.reuters.com/sustainability/sustainable-finance-reporting/bbva-krk-form-climate-focused-strategic-partnership-2024-09-27/>
4. Climate Bonds Initiative. Global Green Finance Market Summary. London, 2023.
5. European Commission. EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities. Brussels, 2022.
6. International Capital Market Association (ICMA). Green Bond Principles. London, 2023.
7. Klein, D. The Paris Agreement on Climate Change: Analysis and Commentary / D. Klein. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017. 447 p. ISBN 978-0-19-880376-8.
8. New Resource Bank (URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/New_Resource_Bank)
9. OECD. Developing Sustainable Finance Definitions and Taxonomies, Paris, 2021.
10. Ozili P.K. Digital finance, green finance and social finance: Is there a link? / PK Ozili // Financial Internet Quarterly. No. 17. P. 1-7. ISSN 2719-3454.
11. Sachs JD The Age of Sustainable Development. New York: Columbia University Press, 2015.
12. Schoenmaker D. Investing for the Common Good. Oxford University Press, 2017.
13. Sustainable finance: Greening the banking sector, Manila, 2024. URL: <https://www.bworldonline.com/opinion/2024/10/11/627075/sustainable-finance-greening-the-banking-sector/>
14. Wang Y. The role of green finance in environmental protection: Two aspects of market mechanism and policies / Y. Wang, Q. Zhi // Energy Procedia. 2016. No. 104. P. 311-316. – ISSN 1876-6102.
15. World Bank. Green Finance and Banking Report, Washington, DC, 2023.
16. Zhou X. Impact of green finance on economic development and environmental quality: a study based on provincial panel data from China / X.Zhou, X.Tang, R.Zhang // Environmental Science and Pollution Research. 2020. No. 27. – P. 19915-19932. – ISSN 0944-1344.
17. Anton Vyacheslavovich Piskarev, “Transformation of Green Financing Mechanisms to Ensure National Environmental Well-Being” dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Economic Sciences, Moscow – 2025.
18. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Commerzbank>
19. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Triad_Bank
20. <https://www.climatepolicyinitiative.org/publication/green-banking-in-china-emerging-trends/>